

**SYNTHESIS OF THE DIETHYL ESTER OF THE DICARBOXYLIC
ACID, C₁₂H₂₀O₄—A DEGRADATION PRODUCT OF THE
SESQUITERPENE, GUAJOL**

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Michael condensation between ethyl 3-methylcyclopentanone-1-carboxylate and ethyl crotonate, followed by hydrolysis and esterification, furnishes (II, R=H) which on Reformatsky's reaction, followed by unsaturation and hydrogenation yields (I, R=Et).

Plattner *et al.* (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1940, 23, 891 ; 1941, 24, 191 ; 1942, 25, 581) obtained the dicarboxylic acid (I, R=H) by the degradation of the sesquiterpene alcohol, guaiol.

The diethyl ester of the acid (I) has been synthesised according to the method of Bhattacharyya (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 214) along the following line.

Ethyl 3-methylcyclopentan-2-one-1-carboxylate is condensed with ethyl crotonate in presence of piperidine in poor yield. But the same condensation with the aid of potassium ethoxide furnishes a good yield of the condensation product (II, R=CO₂Et). Moreover, no appreciable disruptive effect of potassium ethoxide on the substituted β-keto ester formed is observed (*cf.* Bhattacharyya, *loc. cit.*). The compound (II, R=CO₂Et) is hydrolysed and esterified. The action of zinc and ethyl bromoacetate on (II, R=H) yields the lactone (III) which on successive treatment with phosphorus pentachloride, alcohol, alcoholic potash and then with sulphuric acid and alcohol gives (IV). On catalytic hydrogenation with Adam's catalyst (I, R=CO₂Et) is obtained.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Ethyl 3-Methylcyclopentan-2-one-1-(β-n-butyrate)-1-carboxylate (II, R = CO₂Et).—*Ethyl 3-methylcyclopentan-2-one-1-carboxylate* (17 c.c., Cornubert and Borrel, *Bull. soc. chim.* 1930, 47, 301) was mixed with ethyl crotonate (17 c.c.) and piperidine (5 c.c.) when the mixture became slightly warm. It was heated on the water-bath for 24 hours. The cooled product was diluted with ether and the ether extract was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and dried. Ether was driven off and the residuc distilled, b.p. 164-66°/7.5 mm., yield 4 g.

The following experiments were carried out according to Bhattacharyya (*loc. cit.*).

The above condensation was performed with the β-keto ester (24 g.) and ethyl crotonate (20 g.) in presence of potassium ethoxide to yield 27 g. of the desired ester. (Found : C, 63.84 ; H, 8.6. C₁₅H₂₄O₅ requires C, 63.98 ; H, 8.44 per cent).

3-Methylcyclopentan-2-one-1-β-n-butyric Acid (II, R = H).—The above compound (23 g.) was hydrolysed and distilled, b.p. 140-150°/2 mm., yield 12 g. (Found : C, 64.83 ; H, 8.21. C₁₀H₁₆O₃ requires C, 65.21 ; H, 8.69 per cent).

Ethyl 3-Methylcyclopentan-2-one-1-β-n-butyrate.—The above acid (12 g.) was esterified with alcohol and sulphuric acid ; b.p. 125-30°/10 mm., yield 11 g. (Found : C, 67.53 ; H, 9.02. C₁₂H₂₀O₃ requires C, 67.92 ; H, 9.43 per cent)

The semicarbazone was prepared as usual and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 156°. (Found : C, 57.77 ; H, 8.5. C₁₃H₂₃O₃N₃ requires C, 57.99 ; H, 8.55 per cent).

δ-Lactone of 2-Hydroxy-2-(carbethoxymethyl)-3-methylcyclopentane-1-β-n-butyric Acid (III).—The Reformatsky's reaction was carried out with the keto-ester (11 g.), ethyl bromoacetate and zinc as usual, b.p. 146-50°/3 mm., yield 7 g. (Found : C, 66.7 ; H, 8.4. C₁₄H₂₂O₄ requires C, 66.15 ; H, 8.6 per cent).

Ethyl 2-Methyl-5-(β-n-butyrate)-cyclopentilidene-acetate. (IV).—Phosphorus pentachloride (5 g.) was slowly added to the above δ-lactonic ester (III, 7 g.). It was then allowed to stand overnight. The clear solution, thus obtained, was poured into alcohol and allowed to stand for 1 hour and then refluxed for 1½ hours. The product was worked up in the usual way. A molecule of hydrochloric acid was split up with methanolic potash and the crude product was esterified with alcohol and sulphuric acid and worked up, b.p. 155°/9 mm., yield 0.8 g. (Found : C, 68.47 ; H, 9.2. C₁₆H₂₆O₄ requires C, 68.09 ; H, 9.22 per cent).

Ethyl 3-Methylcyclopentane-2-carbethoxymethyl-1-β-n-butyrate (I).—The above unsaturated ester was hydrogenated and distilled, b.p. 156°/11 mm. (Found : C, 67.3 ; H, 9.65. C₁₆H₂₆O₄ requires C, 67.6 ; H, 9.86 per cent).

The ester on hydrolysis furnished a gummy acid which failed to crystallise.

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